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ELECTRONIC CIRCUITS EMBEDDED INTO COMPOSITE AEROSPACE MATERIALS

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#ICCM22

Project Aim

- ❑ More efficient utilization of internal volume available on many civilian and military platforms, especially Unmanned Aerial Systems
- ❑ Develop a technique for the integration of electronic devices, mainly radiolocation and communication systems, in into multi-functional aerospace composites structure

Radar and other avionics in the nose of a Cessna Citation I/SP

F-105 Thunderchief with avionics laid out

Composite PCB Components

Dielectric - Structural Glass HexPly 914E

Conducting Materials:

Copper electroplated carbon-nickel veil

Voltera Flexible Conducting Silver Ink

Composite PCB Components

Vias - through hole, blind and buried

Electronic
Components
Connections

RF Four Way Switch Embedded into Composite Structure

RF Switching Network

The Switch control circuit

Switch Assembly

Fabricated Composite Switch

Bottom side view

Top side view

Measurement Results

Thank you for your attention